

Evaluation of Potassium Quantity-Intensity Relationships in some Soils of West Bengal

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Studies on quantity/intensity (Q/I) relations of potassium (K^+) have been conducted using six soils of West Bengal with contrasting properties. Several important parameters have been evaluated, and their dependence on soil properties discussed. The pool size of labile K^+ as well as its lability in soils have been found to follow the equilibrium activity ratios (AR_K^E). The influence of Gapon exchange selectivity coefficients (K_G) on Q/I relationships of the given soils is also ascertained. The approximate validity of the $(CEC \cdot K_G)$ products, leading to the PBC^K of the soils, was put to a test for the given soils with encouraging results. The use of interpolated K_G values at $\Delta K_{exch}^+ = 0$ in assessing the K^+ availability in the given soils has been further examined.

Solution-exchange phase equilibria in soils play a fundamental role in controlling the ready availability of nutrients to plants, and also leaching loss as well as chemical or microbiological transformations of cations in soil. Potassium, calcium, magnesium are some of the cations that have undergone the most extensive testing in soil systems in terms of solution-exchange phase interactions¹. The approach often used to predict K^+ availability in soil solutions is the quantity-intensity (Q/I) study². The latter involves the change in exchangeable K^+ (quantity) as a function of K^+

activity ratio, $(a_K / \sqrt{a_{Ca+Mg}})$ (intensity). This study has been used for better understanding of K^+ release into the soil solution and consequent uptake by plants³. From the Q/I plot, several parameters may be obtained to characterise the K^+ status release dynamics of soil K^+ , namely, the equilibrium activity ratio for K^+ (AR_K^E), labile or exchangeable $K(-\Delta K_0)$, linear potential buffering capacity for K^+ (PBC^K) and specifically fixed $K^+(K_x)^4$.

Theoretical :

For the $K-(Ca + Mg)$ interactions, the Gapon equation leads to the relation,

$$K_G = \frac{\text{Exch } K \cdot [a_{Ca+Mg}]^{1/2}}{(\text{Exch } Ca + \text{Exch } Mg) \cdot a_K} \quad (1)$$

where K_G is the Gapon cation-exchange selectivity coefficient, Exch is the exchangeable cations in $\text{cmol}(p^+) \text{kg}^{-1}$ and a is the activity for the cations shown. Although K_G is not a true thermodynamic parameter, it is assumed to have an indistinguishable thermodynamic value for ranges of monovalent ion exchange phase loadings encountered in agricultural soil systems⁵. Equation (1) can be rearranged in the form,

$$(\text{Exch } K) = (\text{Exch } Ca + \text{Exch } Mg) K_G (a_K) [a_{Ca+Mg}]^{1/2}$$

$$\text{or, } (\text{Exch } K) = (\text{Exch } Ca + \text{Exch } Mg) K_G AR_K^E \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{d(\text{Exch } K)}{d(AR_K^E)} = (\text{Exch } Ca + \text{Exch } Mg) K_G$$

$$\text{or, } PBC^K = (\text{Exch } Ca + \text{Exch } Mg) K_G \quad (3)$$

For most agricultural soils under K fertilisation, the contribution of Exch K to the CEC is insignificant¹, i.e. $(\text{Exch } Ca + \text{Exch } Mg) \gg \text{Exch } K$, so that equation (3) may be approximated as

$$PBC^K \cong CEC \cdot K_G \quad (4)$$

where CEC refers to the cation exchange capacity of soils.

In the present study, the Q/I parameters for K^+ dynamics in six soils of West Bengal have been evaluated. Attempts were also made to ascertain the influence of the Gapon

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS

Soil location	Soil order	pH(1 : 2.5) Soil : water suspension	EC (1 : 2.5) dS m ⁻¹	CEC cmol(p ⁺)kg ⁻¹	Organic carbon g kg ⁻¹	Clay %	Exchangeable bases cmol(p ⁺) kg ⁻¹ Na ⁺	
							(Ca ²⁺ + Mg ²⁺)	Na ⁺
Gayeshpur	P-7	6.53	0.15	25.3	8.2	35.8	6.5	0.55
	P-9	5.98	0.13	24.2	6.1	28.5	6.1	0.43
Jhargram	Block-I	5.22	0.04	9.20	3.5	14.3	2.6	0.27
	Block-III	5.30	0.04	8.91	2.3	15.2	3.3	0.29
Memari	Inceptisol	6.35	0.10	22.1	7.1	32.4	7.0	0.62
Goaltore	Alfisol	4.80	0.08	10.1	4.1	13.9	2.5	0.32

selectivity coefficient (K_G) for K-(Ca + MG) exchange in soils on Q/I relationship, as well as the relationship of PBC^K and CEC with Q/I parameters of the given soils.

Results and Discussion

The important properties of the soils are presented in Table 1. The soils are normal to acidic in pH. The samples from Gayeshpur and Memari had high CEC and organic matter content as compared to other soils. The sample P-7 of Gayeshpur was high in clay content among the given soils. Table 2 gives a summary of the distribution of different forms of soil K^+ . The nonexchangeable K^+ or reserve

TABLE 2—DISTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENT FORMS OF POTASSIUM IN SOILS

Soil location	Water soluble K	Exchangeable K $cmol(p^+) kg^{-1}$	Nonexchangeable K
Gayeshpur			
P-7	0.49	0.81	3.38
P-9	0.17	0.20	3.30
Jhargram			
Block-I	0.16	0.21	0.48
Block-III	0.13	0.13	0.45
Memari	0.26	0.40	3.36
Goaltore	0.08	0.08	0.42

K being an index of K availability under stress situation, the given soils from Gayeshpur and Memari are expected to release K under stress situation more effectively than the other soils studied (Table 2). This seems to be directly related to the dominance in clay fraction of the soils of micaceous minerals. The mineralogical analysis data of some representative soils are shown in Table 3. The data revealed the presence of substantial amounts of

TABLE 3—SEMIQUANTITATIVE COMPOSITION OF CLAY FRACTION OF SOILS

Soil location*	Smectite	Chlorite	Illite	Kaolinite
Gayeshpur				
P-7 ^a	2.05	30.58	40.32	27.05
P-9 ^a	8.20	29.71	50.80	11.29
Jhargram				
Block-I	-	-	36.29	63.71
Memari ^a	19.03	-	61.71	19.26

*Inter-stratified : ^a Present.

illite in Gayeshpur and Memari soils, the former being the most dominant clay mineral in these soils. The soils from Gayeshpur also contained substantial amounts of chlorite, while the soils from Memari was considerably rich in smectite. On the other hand, Jhargram soil (and presumably Goaltore soil having rather similar properties) was dominant in kaolinite possessing hardly any specific sites for K.

Figs. 1 and 2 show the Q/I plots of two representative soils, namely, Gayeshpur (P-7) and Goaltore soils. The form of these Q/I curves was characterised by an upper linear

Fig. 1. Q/I curve for Gayeshpur (P-7) soil.

Fig. 2. Q/I curve for Gayeshpur (P-7) soil.

part (non-specific sites for K adsorption and similar to that encountered for Gapon's exchange relationship) and a curvilinear part at low equilibrium activity ratio (AR^K) values, attributed to exchange with high specific affinity for K^+ . Table 4 records various Q/I parameters.

LeRoux⁶ noted that ΔK_0 was a better estimate of soil labile K than the normal exchangeable K^+ . He found that a higher value of labile K ($-\Delta K_0$) indicated a greater K^+ release into the soil solution, resulting in a large pool of labile K. Again, among the different parameters of Q/I relationship, labile K ($-\Delta K_0$) was found to be the best index